

Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative - 2012 NBI-funded Research Report

Population genetics of invasive weeds *Centaurea maculosa* and *Centarea jacea* on Nantucket Island

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Abstract

Centaurea maculosa (Spotted Knapweed) and *Centaurea jacea* (Brown Knapweed) are members of the Composite family (Asteraceae) and natives of Eurasia. *C. maculosa* is a major invasive species in North America, dominating large stretches of grassland. Both species were introduced on Nantucket island, and aim of this study is to describe genetic structure and diversity of these weeds. Analyses based on chloroplast DNA sequence data suggest just one introduction of these species on Nantucket island. The only outlier appears to be a specimen H5, and based on its morphology it was suggested that we found a specimen of *Centaurea nigrescens* on Nantucket island that has not been described there before. The further analysis of nuclear DNA with microsatellite markers might elucidate a potential gene flow and hybridization between these two species as all hybrid-like plant specimen clustered together with *C. jacea* cpDNA sequences, suggesting environmental plasticity of brown knapweed and not a genetic diversity.

Introduction

Centaurea maculosa Lam. (Spotted Knapweed, syn. *C. stoebe* L.) in the Composite family is a major invasive weed in North America. Native to eastern Europe and western Asia, it was introduced as a contaminant in alfalfa and clover seed around 1890 with possible separate introductions in the early 1900's (Broennimann et al, 2007). It is present in 46 states and listed as a noxious weed in 17 (USDA Plants Database). Spotted Knapweed thrives in a wide range of habitats and soil types, but is most adapted to relatively dry conditions with well-drained soil; its taproot allows it to reach deeper water sources. This species invades disturbed as well as natural areas such as roadsides, fields, meadows, forest edges and prairies. Range lands in Western US and Canada are most adversely affected by spotted knapweed, where it can become the dominant species, suppressing native plants and reducing the productive value of the land. More than 3 million hectares across US and Canada have been covered by spotted knapweed, at a cost of millions of dollars in economic damages (Story et al, 2006). Spotted knapweed has been the focus of a large biocontrol effort in western United States, where twelve insect species have already been introduced to control it (Story et al, 2006). Such efforts, however, often do not take into account the biological origin and diversity of the invasive populations.

The taxonomy and evolutionary history of *C. maculosa* is not well understood. In its native range, spotted knapweed is either diploid or tetraploid, while, to date, only tetraploids have been found in North America (Broennimann et al, 2007). Recently, the *C. maculosa* "complex" has been reassessed and Ochsmann (2001) describes two subspecies: *C. stoebe* ssp. *stoebe*, a diploid annual; and *C. stoebe* ssp. *micranthos* (syn *C. biebersteinii*) a tetraploid, short-lived polycarpic perennial. While both may have been introduced, only *C. stoebe* ssp. *micranthos* becomes invasive, possibly due to its perennial habit. *C. jacea* (Brown Knapweed) is also an European weed introduced to North America, and its taxonomy studies suggest to refer to this plant as *C. jacea* species complex.

In plants, certain life-history features are more likely to be found in invasive than in non-invasive populations. They include short generation time, fast growth, self-compatibility, general habitat requirements, substantial developmental plasticity, resistance to environmental stress, predation and disease resistance, high reproductive output, small seeds, efficient dispersal mechanisms, and variable seed dormancy (Rogers & Siemann, 2005). Some species arrive in a novel habitat with a genome plasticity as an adaptation tool, but there is usually a time gap between the establishment of local populations and a range expansion of an invasive plant (Kowarik 1995). In some cases invasive spread appears to be a consequence of evolutionary changes that make the species more competitive in its new environment (Callaway & Maron, 2006).

The recent data indicate that the North American invasive spotted knapweed possesses several advantages over other conspecific but non-invasive populations in Europe. North American *C. maculosa* seeds germinate more readily than their European accessions and the resulting individuals are larger, more robust, and better able to fend off and compensate for herbivore attack by chemical means, under both greenhouse and field conditions. This suggests that evolutionary processes during or after introduction, such as hybridization, *in situ* selection, often contribute to invasiveness (Whitney et al. 2006). Despite progress toward understanding the ecology of invasive plants and recipient communities (Callaway et al. 2004), little progress has been made in identifying the genetic changes (Rieseberg et al. 2006).

The threat of invasive species to native biodiversity has become a prime concern among conservation biologists and New England flora. Nantucket invasive plant species list recognizes spotted knapweed as highly invasive. There are several factors that help a non-native species colonize a new environment. One of them is the ability to hybridize with closely related species. There has been observed a potential hybridization of spotted knapweed with another introduced species - brown knapweed (*C. jacea*). Plants with the hybrid morphology were seen and collected on the Nantucket island.

Hypothesis 1: *C. maculosa* and *C. jacea* form hybrids on Nantucket island. Hybridization can be sometimes detected from morphological intermediates, but must be confirmed by with DNA analysis. Individuals with hybrid ancestry will show mosaics of alleles from both species.

Ho: Morphological intermediates resembling hybrids between *C. maculosa* and *C. jacea* are just extreme phenotypes of these species caused by environmental conditions.

Hypothesis 2: *C. maculosa* was introduced several times to Nantucket island, and there has been a gene flow between island populations.

Ho: *C. maculosa* was introduced just once to Nantucket island, and all the populations are genetically uniform.

Methods and Study sites

In order to study spotted knapweed hybridization, we sampled several spotted and brown knapweed populations on Nantucket island (Table 1, Figures 1 - 3), and we collected leaf tissue and seeds from five hybrid-like plants. Total DNA was extracted using the FAST DNA Plant kit (Mobio) according the manufacturer's protocol.

We used the *atpB-rbcL* and *trnL-trnF* chloroplast intergenic region markers (Chiang et al, 1998). PCR was carried out in a 25ul volume reaction with 5ul DNA, 2.5ul of 2.5 mM MgCl₂, 2.5ul of 2 mM dNTPs, 2.5ul of 10x reaction buffer, 1ul of each primer (10 mM) and 0.2ul of *Taq* polymerase (5 units/ul). The PCR conditions were 95°C for 5min, 35 cycles of 95°C for 30s, AT for 30s (50°C for ITS, 52°C for *atpB-rbcL*), 72°C for 45s, and a final extension of 72°C for 5min. Amplified fragments were sequenced using an ABI PRISM 3100 Avant Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). Sequence editing and alignment was performed using the program Sequencher 3.1 (GeneCodes).

From a single tetraploid individual, 39,954 EST covering 29 Mb were sequenced as part of the Composite Genome Project (<http://compgenomics.ucdavis.edu/>). All microsatellites or simple sequence repeats (SSRs), within these ESTs were retrieved and 3 and 4 bp motifs were further analyzed (Table 2). We plan to utilize 10 microsatellite markers, and after PCR amplification, the products were be scored by fragment analysis to reveal the inter- and intra-specific polymorphism. We will analyze the nucleart data in programs Arlequin and HP. Genetic relationships based on marker similarities were visualized in a programs Structure and Distruct We will compare the genetic data of the collected plant material on Nantucket with other 52 *C. maculosa* accessions obtained from native and invasive ranges of this plant.

Results

The aligned trnL-trnF cpDNA region was 424bp in length and contained 4 polymorphic sites (Figure 4). The chloroplast DNA analysis showed a total of 3 haplotypes, with two major clusters separated by one T indel (insertion- deletion) and C-G base substitution. One cluster contains all *C. maculosa* sequences. All *C. jacea* and hybrid-like specimen fall into the other group. The third group was represented but just one sequence - specimen H5 had a 14bp insertion/ deletion and one A indel.

Discussion

C. maculosa tetraploids appear to be more successful in their introduced range of North America than in their native European range. The Enemy Release hypothesis (Keane & Crawley 2002) may partially explain the success of *C. maculosa* as an invader, especially since it appears the ploidy change correlates with the change in life history—from annual diploid to biennial and polycarpic tetraploid. Specialized root feeders, which can kill plants that overwinter after seed set, may have selected *C. maculosa* with a predominantly monocarpic habit in Europe, while the polycarpic tetraploids were able to

spread in North America in the absence of this selective pressure (Müller-Schärer et al 2004).

Considering the diversity of *C. maculosa* tetraploids and *C. jacea* species complex in North America, it was surprising that our chloroplast sequence data indicate just one introduction of these species on the island. The further analysis of nuclear DNA might elucidate the potential gene flow and hybridization between these two species as all hybrid-like plant specimen clustered together with *C. jacea* sequences, suggesting environmental plasticity of brown knapweed and not genetic diversity.

The only outlier in this DNA analysis appears to be a specimen H5 and based on its morphology it was suggested that we found a specimen of *Centaurea nigrescens* on Nantucket island that has not been described there before.

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Table 1: Collection Sites for *Centaurea* population genetics study. Sample numbers correspond with numbers on the map in Figures 1 -3. Species IDs in the left column were based on keying out specimens based on plant growth habit, leaf and flower characteristics.

Scientific Name	Sample	Date	Location Description	Collector
CS1 - <i>C. mac</i>	T3	8/22/2012	Field, Land Bank, 151 Hummock Pond Road, NT	KAO, TZ
CS2 - <i>C. mac</i>	T1, T2	8/22/2012	Bike path, Second Bridge , Madaket Road	KAO, TZ
CS3 - <i>C. mac</i>	5, 6, 7	7/25/2012	Bike path, Sanford Farm , 120 Madaket Road, NT	KAO
CS4 - <i>C. mac</i>		11/22/2012	Mansfield Hollow Dam, CT	BC
CS5 - <i>C. mac</i>		9/17/2013	Morrissey Blvd., Boston MA	TZ
CJ1 - <i>C. jac</i>	1, 13	7/23/2012	Bike path, 118 Cliff Road	KAO
CJ2 - <i>C. jac</i>	2, 3, 4	7/23/2012	Bike path, Folgers Marsh, 180 Polpis Road	KAO
CJ3 - <i>C. jac</i>	E	9/10/2012	Nanahumacke, 149 Hummock Pond Road	ES
H1 - <i>C. jac/hyb?</i>	H	2010	Land Bank, Barrett Farm Road	KAO, GEK
H2 - <i>C. jac/hyb?</i>		9/21/2011	Bike Path	KAO
H3 - <i>C. jac/hyb?</i>	D	9/4/2012	Land Bank, Barrett Farm Road	KAO
H4 - <i>C. jac/hyb?</i>	F	9/4/2012	Land Bank, Barrett Farm Road	KAO
H5 - <i>C. jac/hyb?</i>		8/22/2012	Bike Path, Polpis Rd	TZ

Table 2: Polymorphic microsatellite markers for *C. maculosa* and *C. jacea*

Locus	Name in CGP library	NCBI ID	Repeat motif in library	Primer sequence (5'-3')
Cm607	XNM2_Contig607	EH737028	(AAC) ₁₁	F: M13-TGGAAGGAGCAACAAACTCA R: GAGTTCGAGTCTGTGCTTGG
Cm730	CNMS730.b2_D16.ab1	EH747930	(CTT) ₂₁	F: M13-GCAGCAACAACCCTTTCTTT R: GGTGGCGATTGAATTGAAGA
Cm1922	CNMS1922.b1_C01.ab1	EH742245	(GAT) ₁₈	F: M13-AATCAATTGGGCGATAGACG R: AGGGTTAGGGTCCATCAACA
Cm2893	XNM2_Contig2893	EH725149	(CTT) ₁₈	F: M13-TCGATGGTCTAGGGTTTCGT R: ATTCGCAATAGCGCCTGTA
Cm4657	CNML4657.b1_A13.ab1	EH718070	(CAG) ₁₂	F: M13-TGAATCCTCGTCACAATTCG R: GGCTGAAATTCATGAAACC
Cm4727	XNM2_Contig4727	EH732312	(CTT) ₁₉	F: M13-TGGTTGCTCTCCCTCTATCC R: CATCCTGCTGAGTTTCATCG
Cm8337	CNMS8337.b1_A22.ab1	EH748991	(GAT) ₁₅	F: M13-GGAATGGGAATTGGAATGTG R: GTGTTGGCATATGATGGATG
Cm9136	CNML9136.b1_P04.ab1	EH722742	(GAA) ₁₀	F: M13-GACGCCTAAATTGCACCATC R: TGCCGATGAGCTAATTCCTT
Cm10060	CNMS10060.b1_G19.ab1	EH736968	(TTG) ₁₆	F: M13-TTGCTGTATGACCCAAATGC R: TTTCACACTTCCACAACATTTTT
Cm11611	CNMS11611.b1_E23.ab1	EH738131	(GTT) ₁₄	F: M13-TGCATAAAGCGCAGAAGATG R: GCCATGGCAAGTTGGAATTA
Cm11753	CNMS11753.b1_A12.ab1	EH738287	(CTT) ₁₁	F: M13-CATATCTATGGCAGCAGCA R: CCAATCTGAAAACAGCATGA
Cm14123	CNMM14123.b1_F04.ab1	EH727682	(GAA) ₁₆	F: M13-ATTTGTTGCCAGACCTCAG R: AGCCAATTTCTACCGTCAA
Cm15223	CNMM15223.b1_M14.ab1	EH728763	(ATCC) ₉	F: M13-CGGTGGTGATTTGGAACAG R: GAACCAAGCACCACGAAATC

Figures 1 – 3: Maps of collection sites on Nantucket island

Centaurea (Knapweed) DNA Collection Locations, 2012

Centaurea (Knapweed) DNA Collection Locations, West End, 2012

Centaurea (Knapweed) DNA Collection Locations, Mid-Island, 2012

	190	200	210	220	230	240
H_D05_ugu_H2_4	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CJ_E03_ugu_CJ2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CJ_A04_ugu_CJ2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_PCR_F05_ugu_H	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CJ_E06_ugu_CJ1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CJ_F06_ugu_cj1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_F03_ugu_CJ2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CJ_C06_ugu_CJ1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_B05_ugu-H2_2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_B04_ugu_H1_P	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_A05_ugu_H2_1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_A06_ugu_H3_3	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CJ_H03_ugu_CJ2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_H05_ugu_H3_2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CJ_H04_ugu_E_P	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CJ_D06_ugu_CJ1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_G05_ugu_H3_1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_E04_ugu_H4_P	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CJ_G03_ugu_CJ2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_C04_ugu_H2_P	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_E05_ugu_H2_5	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_C05_ugu_H2_3	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_D04_ugu_H3_P	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
H_F04_ugu_H5_P	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_E02_ugu_CSB	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_E01_ugu_CS2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_G02_ugu-CSB	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_G01_ugu_CS2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_D01_ugu_CS1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_F02_ugu_CSB	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_C03_ugu_CSCT	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_C02_ugu_CS3	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_C01_ugu_CS1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_B03_ugu_CSCT	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_B02_ugu_CS3	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_A02_ugu_CS3	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_A03_ugu_CSCT	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_F01_ugu_CS2	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_A01_ugu_CS1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_B01_ugu_CS1	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_D03_ugu_CSCT	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_D02_ugu_CS3	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC
CM_H02_ugu_CSB	TTATCA	CAATGAAATATTA	TTTTTTTT	CTTTTTTAATTA	AAAAAA	GGAGTC

	250	260	270	280	290	300
H_D05_ugu_H2_4	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CJ_E03_ugu_CJ2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CJ_A04_ugu_CJ2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_PCR_F05_ugu_H	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CJ_E06_ugu_CJ1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CJ_F06_ugu_cj1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_F03_ugu_CJ2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CJ_C06_ugu_CJ1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_B05_ugu-H2_2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_B04_ugu_H1_P	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_A05_ugu_H2_1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_A06_ugu_H3_3	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CJ_H03_ugu_CJ2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_H05_ugu_H3_2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CJ_H04_ugu_E_PR	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CJ_D06_ugu_CJ1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_G05_ugu_H3_1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_E04_ugu_H4_P	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CJ_G03_ugu_CJ2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_C04_ugu_H2_P	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_E05_ugu_H2_5	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_C05_ugu_H2_3	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_D04_ugu_H3_P	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
H_F04_ugu_H5_P	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_E02_ugu_CSB	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_E01_ugu_CS2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_G02_ugu-CSB	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_G01_ugu_CS2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_D01_ugu_CS1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_F02_ugu_CSB	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_C03_ugu_CSCT	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_C02_ugu_CS3	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_C01_ugu_CS1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_B03_ugu_CSCT	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_B02_ugu_CS3	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_A02_ugu_CS3	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_A03_ugu_CSCT	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_F01_ugu_CS2	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_A01_ugu_CS1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_B01_ugu_CS1	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_D03_ugu_CSCT	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_D02_ugu_CS3	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA
CM_H02_ugu_CSB	GACCGTTC	CAAGTATT	CGAAATTC	GCATCGGT	AAATGAGT	TGGAAAGCGAGACAGATGTA

Table 2: Polymorphic microsatellite markers for *C. maculosa*

Locus	Name in CGP library	NCBI ID	Repeat motif in library	Primer sequence (5'-3')
Cm607	XNM2_Contig607	EH737028	(AAC) ₁₁	F: M13-TGGAAGGAGCAACAAACTCA R: GAGTTCGAGTCTGTGCTTGG
Cm730	CNMS730.b2_D16.ab1	EH747930	(CTT) ₂₁	F: M13-GCAGCAACAACCCTTTCTTT R: GGTGGCGATTGAATTGAAGA
Cm1922	CNMS1922.b1_C01.ab1	EH742245	(GAT) ₁₈	F: M13-AATCAATTGGGCGATAGACG R: AGGGTTAGGGTCCATCAACA
Cm2893	XNM2_Contig2893	EH725149	(CTT) ₁₈	F: M13-TCGATGGTCTAGGGTTTCGT R: ATTCGCAATAGCGCCTGTA
Cm4657	CNML4657.b1_A13.ab1	EH718070	(CAG) ₁₂	F: M13-TGAATCCTCGTCACAATTCG R: GGCTGAAATTCATGAAACC
Cm4727	XNM2_Contig4727	EH732312	(CTT) ₁₉	F: M13-TGGTTGCTCTCCCTCTATCC R: CATCCTGCTGAGTTTCATCG
Cm8337	CNMS8337.b1_A22.ab1	EH748991	(GAT) ₁₅	F: M13-GGAATGGGAATTGGAATGTG R: GTGTTGGCATATGATGGATG
Cm9136	CNML9136.b1_P04.ab1	EH722742	(GAA) ₁₀	F: M13-GACGCCTAAATTGCACCATC R: TGCCGATGAGCTAATTCCTT
Cm10060	CNMS10060.b1_G19.ab1	EH736968	(TTG) ₁₆	F: M13-TTGCTGTATGACCCAAATGC R: TTTCACACTTCCACAACATTTTT
Cm11611	CNMS11611.b1_E23.ab1	EH738131	(GTT) ₁₄	F: M13-TGCATAAAGCGCAGAAGATG R: GCCATGGCAAGTTGGAATTA
Cm11753	CNMS11753.b1_A12.ab1	EH738287	(CTT) ₁₁	F: M13-CATATCTATGGCAGCAGCA R: CCAATCTGAAAACAGCATGA
Cm14123	CNMM14123.b1_F04.ab1	EH727682	(GAA) ₁₆	F: M13-ATTTGTTGCCAGACCTCAG R: AGCCAATTTCTACCGTCAA
Cm15223	CNMM15223.b1_M14.ab1	EH728763	(ATCC) ₉	F: M13-CGGTGGTGATTTGGAACAG R: GAACCAAGCACCACGAAATC